

Tarahara, Parwanipur, Rampur, and Surkhet screening nurseries in 1985-87 were reviewed.

In the tests, 848 entries were evaluated for BI resistance and 644 for BB

resistance: 366 (43.2%) were resistant to BI and 61 (9.5%) to BB. Of these, 13 lines/varieties had resistance to both diseases.

Janaki, Laxmi, and KAU1727

showed high field resistance to both pathogens at all sites (see table) and might be useful parental materials. Janaki and Laxmi are released varieties. □

Resistance of upland rice varieties to pale yellow mottle virus (PYMV) disease in Sierra Leone

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PYMV disease occurs sporadically in Sierra Leone, and its incidence is increasing. Several plots in the eastern and northern provinces have had fairly high levels of infection, and the potential for considerable yield loss is high.

We tested eight released varieties and promising lines for resistance to PYMV under upland conditions at Kenema in the eastern province. Varieties were sown in 10-m² plots in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. One set of varieties was inoculated 3 wk after seeding with sap from blended infected leaves. One set was not inoculated. All treatments received standard fertilizer application and cultural management.

ROK16 was resistant to the virus;

Response of 8 rice cultivars to inoculation with pale yellow mottle virus disease. Sierra Leone, 1983-84 wet season.

Treatment	Mean yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)	Mean height (cm)	Stunting (%)	Reaction ^a
ROK16	2.9		112		
ROK16 + virus	2.7	9	110	1.8	R
Lac 23	2.3		112		
Lac 23 + virus	1.1	54	106	5.4	I
ROK3	2.2		124		
ROK3 + virus	0.3	88	96	22.6	S
Tox 502-SLR	1.7		112		
Tox 502-SLR + virus	1.4	19	104	7.1	I
PN623-3	2.4		110		
PN623-3 + virus	0.3	88	70	36.4	S
IRAT8	1.6		93		
IRAT8 + virus	1.3	20	78	16	I
Tox 516-12-SLR	2.8		65		
Tox 516-12-SLR +virus	0.4	84	42	35.4	S
ROK15	2.9		109		
ROK15 + virus	0.1	97	74	32.1	S
LSD (0.05)	522		10		
CV (%)	19.3		6.4		

^aR = resistant: no infection, or faint and barely discernible leaf mottling. I = intermediate: mild leaf streaking or mottling with or without stunting. S = susceptible: evident chlorosis and leaf mottling with mild to severe stunting.

Tox 502-SLR, IRAT8, and Lac 23 gave intermediate responses (see table).

Despite its intermediate rating, Lac 23 had a significant yield reduction (54%).

PN623-3, Tox 516-12-SLR, ROK3, and ROK15, all rated as susceptible, gave significant yield reductions (84-97%).□

Development of a japonica rice variety with blast (BI) and bacterial blight (BB) resistance

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Resistances to BI and BB are not as strong in japonica rice varieties as in indica varieties. We used indica variety Tetep and japonica variety Toride 1 as BI-resistant parents and made crosses with traditional high-yielding japonica variety Aijing 23 that has BB resistance.

Japonica variety Chengte 232 derived

from Aijing 231/Ailoqing/Toride 1///Aijing 23//Nonghong 23/Tetep has been released. In artificial inoculation tests, it was resistant or moderately resistant to 13 of 14 local strong *Pyricularia oryzae* isolates and 5 *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* races (Table 1). It has 139-d duration in

Table 1. Reaction^a of Chengte 232 to 14 *P. oryzae* isolates and *S. campestris* pv. *oryzae* races. Hangzhou, China.

Variety	Reaction ^b to BI														Reaction ^b to BB					
	A1	A61	A63	B1	B15	C3	C13	C15	D1	D3	E1	E3	F1	G1	188	186	98	35	149	
Chengte 232	R	R	R	MR	R	R	MR	R	R	MR	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Nonghu 6	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	MR	MR	MR	R
Tetep	S	R	S	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	MR	R	R	R						
Aijing 23	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	MR	MR	R	R	R	R

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible. ^bGrouping or race number based on Chinese differentials.